

**A NEW CONUS (GASTROPODA: CONIDAE) SPECIES
FOUND IN MARTINIQUE**

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The first author is delighted that attention can again be drawn to LOZET & PETRON'S "Coquillages des Antilles" (1977) concerning the various very colorful conid species illustrated thereat in page 107, as a result of additional study material having been acquired by the second author, leading to conclusions we have reached from our studies that one more of those attractive species can be given an identity of its own, which we are describing hereunder as a new taxon:

Conus (Dauciconus) norai sp. nov.

Description: Shell obconic, of medium size, with a flat spire consisting of 10 whorls and having an exerted apex with a yellowish-white protoconch; surface of whorls being flat and moderately incised with shallow spiral threads, the last five whorls curving concavely as its edges fold into canaliculated suture, with the penultimate whorl forming a sharply carinate shoulder. The sides are convexly parallel above, then taper gradually towards the anterior end, where it is wrinkled several ridges. The ground color of the shell is distinctly violet, with the spire being ornamented with a series of white-and-chocolate tessellations; the body whorl being splashed with uneven cloudy brownish flammules, separated at its mid-section by a belt of violet, edged with irregular dark brown dashes. The aperture is tinted a nacreous light violet.

Habitat: Usually found in sandy bottom with rocks and algae but no other vegetation at about 10 meters depth.

Type locality: Pte de la Baleine, south west coast of Martinique.

Distribution: Within a stretch from Pte du Diamant northward to Anse Dufour and again north of St. Pierre in the south west coast of Martinique.

Holotype: 37.4 mm x 22.8 mm deposited in the Musée d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva, under No. MHNG 16150.

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Paratypes: No. 1 — 32.8 mm x 18.2 mm deposited in the Staatliches Museum for Naturkunde, Stuttgart (SMNS) with the Inv. N.: ZI 8468

No. 2 — 28.3 x 15.2 mm in coll. António Nora, Portugal

No. 3 — 36.7 x 21.0 mm in coll. Dieter Röckel, Germany

No. 4 — 42.0 x 23.5 mm deposited in the American Museum of Natural History, New York

No. 5 — 35.8 x 19.7 mm in coll. Gabriella Raybaudi, Italy

No. 6 — 29.0 x 16.5 mm in coll. António Monteiro, Portugal.

External Morphology (of animal): syphon is a deep yellow, with a yellow foot rimmed with a ring of regular black smearings.

Discussion: The contours of the new species immediately associate it with *Conus daucus*, commonly called the "carrot cone", which has a wide distributional range throughout the Caribbean region. The shape of the shells has a spire which varies from very depressed, with concave sides, to being somewhat elevated, with flat sides. While the overall shape is very constant, the color is quite variable and seen in dark orange, orange yellow, light olive yellow, light or dark brown and, somewhat rarely, in white with a pale yellow base. Shells are tinted invariably in solid colors and may have a colorless midsection band or not, with occasionally a second pale band just below the shoulder. No study is known which has attempted to segregate and associate specific color, size or shape with specific localities; but, as can be expected, such a ubiquitous complex would have spread widely throughout areas where quite different conditions prevail. Martinique appears to be a particular locality where various allopatric populations have taken root, with a propensity for diversity of coloration not seen anywhere else. *C. boui* DA MOTTA, 1988, a species with a ground color of golden-brown, and having its body whorl decorated with undulating streamers of axially-aligned strands of dark brown, overflowing nearly two-thirds of its surface, is one such distinct population. *C. boui* is usually found in depths of 18 to 37 meters. The new species is found allopatrically within an intervening strata between shallow waters, where a larger than average sized *daucus* (about 50 mm) of light to dark brown color occurs and the lower depths of the habitat of *C. boui*. In addition to its consistent purplish coloration, the animal of the new species is distinguishable by the distinct differences of color as illustrated, compared to those of its two neighbors.

The conclusion that *C. norai* is a distinct population is based on the grounds (a) that it is found allopatrically from the habitat of other look-alikes; (b) it has a consistent purplish ground color as well as its own pattern of decoration, and (c) the animal itself is painted quite differently from *daucus* or *boui* to be instantly recognized as distinct.

It would be of interest to add that the figure 193 in LOZET & PETRON (1977) was described by PETUCH (1986) as *C. riosi*, although he mentioned that his own study material was trawled off Salvador in depths of 50 meters thereby leaving only the

scarlet colored species, also found in Martinique, to await further study for determination of its proper status.

Etymology: We dedicate this new taxon as a token of our friendship for Antonio Nora of Oporto, Portugal and in appreciation of his devotion to the study of Conidae shared mutually between us.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- DA MOTTA, A. J. (1988) — Publicações Opcionais da Sociedade Portuguesa de Malacologia N.º 11 (Lisboa)
- GLENCH, W. J. (1942) — The genus *Conus* in the Western Atlantic — *Johnsonia* 1 (6): 1-40.
- KOHN, A. J. (1968) — Type specimens and identity of the described species of *Conus* IV. The species described by Hwass, Bruguiere and Olivi in 1792 — *J. Linn. Soc.* 47: 185-227.
- LOZET & PETRON (1977) — *Coquillages des Antilles*.
- SOWERBY, G. B. (1832-1841) — *The conchological illustrations*, London.
- USTICKE, G.N. (1968) — Caribbean cones from St. Croix and the Lesser Antilles — 1-30 (Narberth).
- VINK, D.N. (1968) — The Conidae of Western Atlantic I — *La Conchiglia (Rome)* XVI (186-187): 18-22 figs.
- WALLS, J. G. (1979) — *Cone shells: a synopsis of the living conidae* — New Jersey (Neptune).

Note:

At the time of going to press, the authors wish to add that, as a result of further field work, it was found that the new species is polychromatic (although still distinct from *boui* and *daucus*) and a second report will be forthcoming as soon as laboratory tests of wet specimens, presently being undertaken, are completed.

A number of 6 differently colored additional paratypes is therefore being designated, ranging in size from the 50-37 mm, which disposition will be later published.

Conus (Dauciconus) norai n.sp.

Fig. 1 — Holotype, MHNG, Geneva. Dorsal, ventral, spire view.

Fig. 2 — Paratype 1, SMNS Stuttgart. Dorsal and ventral view.

Fig. 3 — Paratype 2. Dorsal and ventral view.

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C. (Dauciconus) boui

C. (D.) norai

C. (D.) daucus

siphon
sole

Conus (Dauciconus) norai n.sp. Comparison of animal color.

Data furnished by patric bou from his personal observations (3.9.1988)

